

Descriptives - Motivation facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	19	.4663	.21399	.04909	.3632	.5695	.00	.90
	Tim	31	.5110	.21623	.03884	.4317	.5903	.11	.90
	Total	50	.4940	.21430	.03031	.4331	.5549	.00	.90
Recall	Abby	19	.5358	.24334	.05583	.4185	.6531	.00	.90
	Tim	31	.6574	.23468	.04215	.5713	.7435	.23	1.00
	Total	50	.6112	.24295	.03436	.5422	.6802	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	19	.4543	.17105	.03924	.3718	.5367	.00	.70
	Tim	31	.5046	.12680	.02277	.4581	.5511	.20	.83
	Total	50	.4855	.14560	.02059	.4441	.5268	.00	.83
Duration	Abby	19	1958.4737	784.22427	179.91339	1580.4897	2336.4577	1183.00	3105.00
	Tim	31	1687.8065	542.14791	97.37264	1488.9450	1886.6679	1060.00	3150.00
	Total	50	1790.6600	650.75907	92.03123	1605.7163	1975.6037	1060.00	3150.00
FirstActDet	Abby	19	252.9474	172.16771	39.49798	169.9652	335.9295	63.00	632.00
	Tim	31	219.9355	195.79682	35.16615	148.1166	291.7543	45.00	742.00
	Total	50	232.4800	186.07002	26.31427	179.5995	285.3605	45.00	742.00
LastActDet	Abby	19	1650.8947	933.38499	214.13320	1201.0176	2100.7719	654.00	3099.00
	Tim	31	1295.8387	511.84556	91.93018	1108.0922	1483.5852	675.00	2678.00
	Total	50	1430.7600	714.66212	101.06849	1227.6553	1633.8647	654.00	3099.00
ProcDur	Abby	19	307.5789	367.69996	84.35616	130.3532	484.8047	6.00	1541.00
	Tim	31	391.9677	283.56816	50.93034	287.9541	495.9814	6.00	1105.00
	Total	50	359.9000	317.19036	44.85749	269.7555	450.0445	6.00	1541.00
FixRel	Abby	19	1.9926	.59441	.13637	1.7061	2.2791	1.14	2.85
	Tim	31	1.7800	.61838	.11106	1.5531	2.0068	.75	2.85
	Total	50	1.8608	.61220	.08658	1.6868	2.0348	.75	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	19	4.1042	3.93988	.90387	2.2053	6.0032	.57	15.70
	Tim	31	5.4897	4.54817	.81688	3.8214	7.1580	.66	15.70
	Total	50	4.9632	4.33918	.61365	3.7300	6.1964	.57	15.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	19	632.7205	353.84944	81.17863	462.1706	803.2705	197.00	1445.73
	Tim	31	571.5581	238.21468	42.78462	484.1802	658.9359	197.00	1177.00
	Total	50	594.7998	285.72228	40.40723	513.5984	676.0012	197.00	1445.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	19	861.4653	418.92451	96.10787	659.5501	1063.3804	179.65	1982.39
	Tim	31	744.9181	369.98679	66.45159	609.2058	880.6303	123.87	1807.04
	Total	50	789.2060	389.28707	55.05351	678.5718	899.8402	123.87	1982.39
TotSac	Abby	19	76.7895	11.47741	2.63310	71.2575	82.3214	54.00	93.00
	Tim	31	75.2581	11.68751	2.09914	70.9711	79.5451	55.00	95.00
	Total	50	75.8400	11.51460	1.62841	72.5676	79.1124	54.00	95.00
Sac2Key	Abby	19	35.7895	10.47526	2.40319	30.7406	40.8384	21.00	55.00
	Tim	31	35.0000	11.36075	2.04045	30.8328	39.1672	19.00	61.00
	Total	50	35.3000	10.93067	1.54583	32.1935	38.4065	19.00	61.00
AvAttention	Abby	19	.8000	.16997	.03899	.7181	.8819	.40	1.00
	Tim	31	.7097	.19554	.03512	.6380	.7814	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.7440	.18969	.02683	.6901	.7979	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	19	.6579	.21165	.04856	.5559	.7599	.30	1.00
	Tim	31	.7129	.18928	.03400	.6435	.7823	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6920	.19778	.02797	.6358	.7482	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	19	.4053	.14327	.03287	.3362	.4743	.10	.60
	Tim	31	.3903	.14687	.02638	.3365	.4442	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3960	.14422	.02040	.3550	.4370	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	19	757.0000	119.40035	27.39232	699.4509	814.5491	503.00	933.00
	Tim	31	811.3871	144.46930	25.94745	758.3953	864.3789	510.00	998.00
	Total	50	790.7200	136.84507	19.35282	751.8291	829.6109	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	19	47.0687	21.13477	4.84865	36.8821	57.2554	10.92	82.27
	Tim	31	40.2556	20.41669	3.66695	32.7667	47.7445	10.92	78.83
	Total	50	43.6621	20.77573	3.25780	39.8244	52.5000	10.92	80.55

	Total	50	42.8446	20.74739	2.93412	36.9483	48.7410	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	19	30.1690	21.62319	4.96070	19.7470	40.5911	1.18	60.08
	Tim	31	24.2926	19.15826	3.44093	17.2653	31.3199	.10	60.08
	Total	50	26.5256	20.11907	2.84527	20.8079	32.2434	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	19	79.4737	13.73304	3.15058	72.8546	86.0928	50.00	90.00
	Tim	31	82.9032	11.60274	2.08391	78.6473	87.1591	50.00	100.00
	Total	50	81.6000	12.43103	1.75801	78.0671	85.1329	50.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	19	18.1579	17.09536	3.92195	9.9182	26.3976	5.00	65.00
	Tim	31	25.9677	21.30803	3.82704	18.1519	33.7836	5.00	70.00
	Total	50	23.0000	20.00000	2.82843	17.3161	28.6839	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	19	49.7368	28.01159	6.42630	36.2357	63.2380	5.00	90.00
	Tim	31	50.0000	33.59067	6.03306	37.6788	62.3212	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	49.9000	31.29012	4.42509	41.0074	58.7926	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	19	70.0000	26.77063	6.14160	57.0970	82.9030	20.00	100.00
	Tim	31	57.9032	41.18605	7.39723	42.7961	73.0104	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	62.5000	36.56487	5.17105	52.1084	72.8916	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	19	71.5789	17.64249	4.04746	63.0755	80.0824	35.00	90.00
	Tim	31	77.2581	14.42444	2.59071	71.9671	82.5490	35.00	100.00
	Total	50	75.1000	15.79492	2.23374	70.6111	79.5889	35.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	19	76.3158	18.91811	4.34011	67.1976	85.4340	45.00	100.00
	Tim	31	59.3548	41.32679	7.42251	44.1961	74.5136	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	65.8000	35.30277	4.99257	55.7671	75.8329	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	19	72.7018	15.73856	3.61067	65.1160	80.2875	45.67	94.67
	Tim	31	69.0215	24.53281	4.40622	60.0228	78.0202	39.00	100.00
	Total	50	70.4200	21.51125	3.04215	64.3066	76.5334	39.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Motivation facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.509	1	38.526	.480
Recall	Welch	3.023	1	37.131	.090
FMeasure	Welch	1.229	1	30.117	.276
Duration	Welch	1.751	1	28.616	.196
FirstActDet	Welch	.390	1	42.009	.536
LastActDet	Welch	2.321	1	24.742	.140
ProcDur	Welch	.733	1	31.040	.398
FixRel	Welch	1.462	1	39.399	.234
FixIrrel	Welch	1.293	1	42.429	.262
AvDurRelFix	Welch	.444	1	28.088	.511
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	.995	1	34.582	.325
TotSac	Welch	.207	1	38.757	.652
Sac2Key	Welch	.063	1	40.636	.804
AvAttention	Welch	2.962	1	42.334	.093
AvMentWL	Welch	.861	1	34.936	.360
AvFam	Welch	.126	1	38.957	.725
AvSCL	Welch	2.078	1	43.689	.157
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	1.256	1	37.181	.270
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.947	1	34.672	.337
NASA_MD	Welch	.824	1	33.364	.370
NASA_PD	Welch	2.031	1	44.429	.161
NASA_TD	Welch	.001	1	43.457	.976
NASA_Performance	Welch	1.583	1	47.777	.214
NASA_Effort	Welch	1.397	1	32.498	.246
NASA_Frustration	Welch	3.891	1	45.212	.055
NASA_Score	Welch	.417	1	47.854	.521

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Information processing facet									
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	39	.5344	.20288	.03249	.4686	.6001	.11	.90
	Tim	11	.3509	.19937	.06011	.2170	.4848	.00	.78
	Total	50	.4940	.21430	.03031	.4331	.5549	.00	.90
Recall	Abby	39	.5800	.21832	.03496	.5092	.6508	.15	.90
	Tim	11	.7218	.30142	.09088	.5193	.9243	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6112	.24295	.03436	.5422	.6802	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	39	.4998	.13616	.02180	.4557	.5439	.20	.83
	Tim	11	.4346	.17256	.05203	.3187	.5505	.00	.62
	Total	50	.4855	.14560	.02059	.4441	.5268	.00	.83
Duration	Abby	39	1703.5641	580.12951	92.89507	1515.5079	1891.6203	1060.00	3150.00
	Tim	11	2099.4545	813.46387	245.26859	1552.9621	2645.9470	1277.00	3105.00
	Total	50	1790.6600	650.75907	92.03123	1605.7163	1975.6037	1060.00	3150.00
FirstActDet	Abby	39	224.8462	184.86375	29.60189	164.9203	284.7721	45.00	742.00
	Tim	11	259.5455	196.85394	59.35370	127.2972	391.7937	67.00	632.00
	Total	50	232.4800	186.07002	26.31427	179.5995	285.3605	45.00	742.00
LastActDet	Abby	39	1262.6923	599.58688	96.01074	1068.3287	1457.0559	654.00	2678.00
	Tim	11	2026.6364	797.35867	240.41269	1490.9635	2562.3092	1208.00	3099.00
	Total	50	1430.7600	714.66212	101.06849	1227.6553	1633.8647	654.00	3099.00
ProcDur	Abby	39	440.8718	310.58342	49.73315	340.1923	541.5513	9.00	1541.00
	Tim	11	72.8182	101.01566	30.45737	4.9549	140.6814	6.00	343.00
	Total	50	359.9000	317.19036	44.85749	269.7555	450.0445	6.00	1541.00
FixRel	Abby	39	1.8944	.61144	.09791	1.6962	2.0926	.90	2.85
	Tim	11	1.7417	.62912	.18969	1.3190	2.1644	.75	2.85
	Total	50	1.8608	.61220	.08658	1.6868	2.0348	.75	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	39	5.9482	4.36233	.69853	4.5341	7.3623	.57	15.70
	Tim	11	1.4709	1.65716	.49965	.3576	2.5842	.66	6.28
	Total	50	4.9632	4.33918	.61365	3.7300	6.1964	.57	15.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	39	506.5587	202.68619	32.45577	440.8555	572.2620	197.00	1106.00
	Tim	11	907.6545	325.39017	98.10883	689.0545	1126.2546	399.71	1445.73
	Total	50	594.7998	285.72228	40.40723	513.5984	676.0012	197.00	1445.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	39	879.5259	346.00144	55.40457	767.3652	991.6866	443.07	1982.39
	Tim	11	468.9809	378.19254	114.02934	214.9077	723.0541	123.87	1356.22
	Total	50	789.2060	389.28707	55.05351	678.5718	899.8402	123.87	1982.39
TotSac	Abby	39	75.5385	11.89393	1.90455	71.6829	79.3940	54.00	95.00
	Tim	11	76.9091	10.51147	3.16933	69.8474	83.9708	58.00	91.00
	Total	50	75.8400	11.51460	1.62841	72.5676	79.1124	54.00	95.00
Sac2Key	Abby	39	34.9487	11.07617	1.77361	31.3582	38.5392	19.00	61.00
	Tim	11	36.5455	10.82002	3.26236	29.2765	43.8144	22.00	55.00
	Total	50	35.3000	10.93067	1.54583	32.1935	38.4065	19.00	61.00
AvAttention	Abby	39	.7846	.16309	.02612	.7317	.8375	.50	1.00
	Tim	11	.6000	.21448	.06467	.4559	.7441	.30	.90
	Total	50	.7440	.18969	.02683	.6901	.7979	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	39	.7231	.18703	.02995	.6624	.7837	.40	1.00
	Tim	11	.5818	.20405	.06152	.4447	.7189	.30	.80
	Total	50	.6920	.19778	.02797	.6358	.7482	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	39	.3897	.13337	.02136	.3465	.4330	.10	.60
	Tim	11	.4182	.18340	.05530	.2950	.5414	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3960	.14422	.02040	.3550	.4370	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	39	768.7436	138.86300	22.23588	723.7294	813.7578	503.00	998.00
	Tim	11	868.6364	99.61654	30.03552	801.7131	935.5597	673.00	998.00
	Total	50	790.7200	136.84507	19.35282	751.8291	829.6109	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	39	43.1901	21.06006	3.37231	36.3632	50.0170	10.92	82.27
	Tim	11	41.6198	20.53561	6.19172	27.8238	55.4158	10.92	75.96
	Total	50	42.4050	20.79784	4.78202	32.0935	52.7164	10.92	79.12

	Total	50	42.8446	20.74739	2.93412	36.9483	48.7410	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	39	23.6250	20.38043	3.26348	17.0184	30.2316	.10	60.08
	Tim	11	36.8098	15.99618	4.82303	26.0634	47.5562	2.81	56.57
	Total	50	26.5257	20.11907	2.84527	20.8079	32.2434	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	39	83.4615	12.41571	1.98810	79.4368	87.4862	50.00	100.00
	Tim	11	75.0000	10.48809	3.16228	67.9540	82.0460	50.00	90.00
	Total	50	81.6000	12.43103	1.75801	78.0671	85.1329	50.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	39	23.7179	22.41117	3.58866	16.4531	30.9828	5.00	70.00
	Tim	11	20.4545	6.50175	1.96035	16.0866	24.8225	10.00	25.00
	Total	50	23.0000	20.00000	2.82843	17.3161	28.6839	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	39	53.8462	32.77639	5.24842	43.2213	64.4710	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	35.9091	20.95450	6.31802	21.8317	49.9865	25.00	90.00
	Total	50	49.9000	31.29012	4.42509	41.0074	58.7926	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	39	71.7949	31.02391	4.96780	61.7381	81.8517	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	29.5455	36.90898	11.12848	4.7497	54.3412	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	62.5000	36.56487	5.17105	52.1084	72.8916	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	39	76.4103	16.30098	2.61025	71.1261	81.6944	35.00	100.00
	Tim	11	70.4545	13.50084	4.07066	61.3846	79.5245	35.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.1000	15.79492	2.23374	70.6111	79.5889	35.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	39	75.7692	27.87516	4.46360	66.7332	84.8053	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	30.4545	37.31317	11.25034	5.3872	55.5219	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	65.8000	35.30277	4.99257	55.7671	75.8329	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	39	75.8547	18.93059	3.03132	69.7181	81.9913	39.00	100.00
	Tim	11	51.1515	19.54503	5.89305	38.0210	64.2820	39.00	94.67
	Total	50	70.4200	21.51125	3.04215	64.3066	76.5334	39.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Information processing facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	7.208	1	16.328	.016
Recall	Welch	2.121	1	13.103	.169
FMeasure	Welch	1.335	1	13.710	.268
Duration	Welch	2.278	1	13.004	.155
FirstActDet	Welch	.274	1	15.344	.608
LastActDet	Welch	8.708	1	13.355	.011
ProcDur	Welch	39.830	1	46.822	.000
FixRel	Welch	.511	1	15.744	.485
FixIrrel	Welch	27.178	1	43.530	.000
AvDurRelFix	Welch	15.065	1	12.270	.002
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	10.487	1	15.058	.005
TotSac	Welch	.137	1	17.912	.715
Sac2Key	Welch	.185	1	16.408	.673
AvAttention	Welch	7.007	1	13.434	.020
AvMentWL	Welch	4.262	1	15.078	.057
AvFam	Welch	.230	1	13.129	.639
AvSCL	Welch	7.145	1	22.210	.014
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.050	1	16.432	.827
HRVar_NN50	Welch	5.126	1	20.142	.035
NASA_MD	Welch	5.132	1	18.699	.036
NASA_PD	Welch	.637	1	47.866	.429
NASA_TD	Welch	4.769	1	25.383	.038
NASA_Performance	Welch	12.019	1	14.234	.004
NASA_Effort	Welch	1.517	1	19.066	.233
NASA_Frustration	Welch	14.017	1	13.309	.002
NASA_Score	Welch	13.895	1	15.703	.002

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Self-efficacy facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	32	.5288	.20815	.03680	.4537	.6038	.11	.90
	Tim	18	.4322	.21692	.05113	.3244	.5401	.00	.90
	Total	50	.4940	.21430	.03031	.4331	.5549	.00	.90
Recall	Abby	32	.5684	.21265	.03759	.4918	.6451	.23	.90
	Tim	18	.6872	.27949	.06588	.5482	.8262	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6112	.24295	.03436	.5422	.6802	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	32	.4942	.13745	.02430	.4447	.5438	.20	.83
	Tim	18	.4699	.16202	.03819	.3893	.5504	.00	.70
	Total	50	.4855	.14560	.02059	.4441	.5268	.00	.83
Duration	Abby	32	1596.0625	551.62031	97.51362	1397.1822	1794.9428	1060.00	3150.00
	Tim	18	2136.6111	683.93267	161.20448	1796.4994	2476.7228	1277.00	3105.00
	Total	50	1790.6600	650.75907	92.03123	1605.7163	1975.6037	1060.00	3150.00
FirstActDet	Abby	32	251.6250	193.06288	34.12902	182.0184	321.2316	63.00	742.00
	Tim	18	198.4444	172.93801	40.76188	112.4444	284.4445	45.00	632.00
	Total	50	232.4800	186.07002	26.31427	179.5995	285.3605	45.00	742.00
LastActDet	Abby	32	1067.5313	423.51616	74.86779	914.8374	1220.2251	654.00	2678.00
	Tim	18	2076.5000	674.68705	159.02526	1740.9860	2412.0140	1208.00	3099.00
	Total	50	1430.7600	714.66212	101.06849	1227.6553	1633.8647	654.00	3099.00
ProcDur	Abby	32	528.5313	271.80353	48.04853	430.5356	626.5269	223.00	1541.00
	Tim	18	60.1111	81.16642	19.13111	19.7480	100.4742	6.00	343.00
	Total	50	359.9000	317.19036	44.85749	269.7555	450.0445	6.00	1541.00
FixRel	Abby	32	1.8994	.62050	.10969	1.6757	2.1231	.90	2.85
	Tim	18	1.7921	.60858	.14344	1.4895	2.0948	.75	2.85
	Total	50	1.8608	.61220	.08658	1.6868	2.0348	.75	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	32	6.1872	4.60098	.81335	4.5284	7.8460	.57	15.70
	Tim	18	2.7872	2.79903	.65974	1.3953	4.1791	.66	9.06
	Total	50	4.9632	4.33918	.61365	3.7300	6.1964	.57	15.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	32	463.6628	173.21825	30.62095	401.2110	526.1147	197.00	894.29
	Tim	18	827.9322	301.12224	70.97519	678.1877	977.6768	397.57	1445.73
	Total	50	594.7998	285.72228	40.40723	513.5984	676.0012	197.00	1445.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	32	858.1878	323.23180	57.13985	741.6503	974.7253	443.07	1807.04
	Tim	18	666.5717	470.53519	110.90621	432.5800	900.5633	123.87	1982.39
	Total	50	789.2060	389.28707	55.05351	678.5718	899.8402	123.87	1982.39
TotSac	Abby	32	75.3750	11.85055	2.09490	71.1024	79.6476	54.00	95.00
	Tim	18	76.6667	11.17771	2.63461	71.1081	82.2252	56.00	92.00
	Total	50	75.8400	11.51460	1.62841	72.5676	79.1124	54.00	95.00
Sac2Key	Abby	32	34.6875	11.54078	2.04014	30.5266	38.8484	19.00	61.00
	Tim	18	36.3889	9.97726	2.35166	31.4273	41.3505	22.00	55.00
	Total	50	35.3000	10.93067	1.54583	32.1935	38.4065	19.00	61.00
AvAttention	Abby	32	.7844	.16086	.02844	.7264	.8424	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.6722	.21910	.05164	.5633	.7812	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.7440	.18969	.02683	.6901	.7979	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	32	.7563	.17949	.03173	.6915	.8210	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.5778	.18005	.04244	.4882	.6673	.30	.80
	Total	50	.6920	.19778	.02797	.6358	.7482	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	32	.3844	.13467	.02381	.3358	.4329	.10	.60
	Tim	18	.4167	.16179	.03813	.3362	.4971	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3960	.14422	.02040	.3550	.4370	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	32	779.9688	145.09074	25.64866	727.6580	832.2795	503.00	998.00
	Tim	18	809.8333	122.41119	28.85259	748.9597	870.7070	621.00	998.00
	Total	50	790.7200	136.84507	19.35282	751.8291	829.6109	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	32	42.1979	20.63759	3.64825	34.7572	49.6385	10.92	78.83
	Tim	18	43.9944	21.49126	5.06554	33.3070	54.6817	10.92	82.27

	Total	50	42.8446	20.74739	2.93412	36.9483	48.7410	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	32	23.6506	20.97159	3.70729	16.0895	31.2116	.10	60.08
	Tim	18	31.6369	17.93008	4.22616	22.7205	40.5533	1.18	56.57
	Total	50	26.5256	20.11907	2.84527	20.8079	32.2434	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	32	84.0625	12.97874	2.29434	79.3832	88.7418	50.00	100.00
	Tim	18	77.2222	10.32163	2.43283	72.0894	82.3550	50.00	90.00
	Total	50	81.6000	12.43103	1.75801	78.0671	85.1329	50.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	32	23.9063	23.13127	4.08907	15.5665	32.2460	5.00	70.00
	Tim	18	21.3889	13.15133	3.09980	14.8489	27.9289	5.00	65.00
	Total	50	23.0000	20.00000	2.82843	17.3161	28.6839	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	32	59.0625	32.56352	5.75647	47.3221	70.8029	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	33.6111	21.19972	4.99682	23.0687	44.1535	5.00	90.00
	Total	50	49.9000	31.29012	4.42509	41.0074	58.7926	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	32	75.1563	29.08509	5.14157	64.6700	85.6425	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	40.0000	38.38658	9.04780	20.9108	59.0892	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	62.5000	36.56487	5.17105	52.1084	72.8916	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	32	76.7188	16.78178	2.96663	70.6683	82.7692	35.00	100.00
	Tim	18	72.2222	13.85027	3.26454	65.3346	79.1098	35.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.1000	15.79492	2.23374	70.6111	79.5889	35.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	32	79.6875	23.99387	4.24156	71.0368	88.3382	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	41.1111	39.16615	9.23155	21.6342	60.5880	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	65.8000	35.30277	4.99257	55.7671	75.8329	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	32	78.2083	18.26404	3.22866	71.6234	84.7932	39.00	100.00
	Tim	18	56.5741	20.20671	4.76277	46.5255	66.6226	39.00	94.67
	Total	50	70.4200	21.51125	3.04215	64.3066	76.5334	39.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Self-efficacy facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	2.348	1	34.147	.135
Recall	Welch	2.453	1	28.232	.128
FMeasure	Welch	.289	1	30.784	.595
Duration	Welch	8.232	1	29.548	.008
FirstActDet	Welch	1.001	1	38.747	.323
LastActDet	Welch	32.952	1	24.706	.000
ProcDur	Welch	82.036	1	39.785	.000
FixRel	Welch	.353	1	35.953	.556
FixIrrel	Welch	10.540	1	47.621	.002
AvDurRelFix	Welch	22.207	1	23.472	.000
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	2.359	1	26.210	.137
TotSac	Welch	.147	1	37.149	.703
Sac2Key	Welch	.299	1	39.842	.588
AvAttention	Welch	3.619	1	27.486	.068
AvMentWL	Welch	11.344	1	35.274	.002
AvFam	Welch	.516	1	30.307	.478
AvSCL	Welch	.598	1	40.586	.444
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.083	1	34.168	.775
HRVar_NN50	Welch	2.018	1	40.182	.163
NASA_MD	Welch	4.184	1	42.326	.047
NASA_PD	Welch	.241	1	47.976	.626
NASA_TD	Welch	11.148	1	46.832	.002
NASA_Performance	Welch	11.413	1	28.143	.002
NASA_Effort	Welch	1.039	1	41.246	.314
NASA_Frustration	Welch	14.418	1	24.340	.001
NASA_Score	Welch	14.137	1	32.456	.001

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

	Total	50	42.8446	20.74739	2.93412	36.9483	48.7410	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	14	33.2430	17.82248	4.76326	22.9526	43.5334	2.81	56.57
	Tim	36	23.9133	20.58249	3.43041	16.9492	30.8775	.10	60.08
	Total	50	26.5256	20.11907	2.84527	20.8079	32.2434	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	14	87.8571	13.68805	3.65828	79.9539	95.7604	50.00	100.00
	Tim	36	79.1667	11.18034	1.86339	75.3838	82.9495	50.00	90.00
	Total	50	81.6000	12.43103	1.75801	78.0671	85.1329	50.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	14	28.2143	27.70776	7.40521	12.2163	44.2123	5.00	70.00
	Tim	36	20.9722	16.11652	2.68609	15.5192	26.4253	5.00	65.00
	Total	50	23.0000	20.00000	2.82843	17.3161	28.6839	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	14	59.6429	36.87110	9.85422	38.3541	80.9316	5.00	100.00
	Tim	36	46.1111	28.51343	4.75224	36.4636	55.7587	5.00	90.00
	Total	50	49.9000	31.29012	4.42509	41.0074	58.7926	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	14	80.7143	23.60387	6.30840	67.0858	94.3428	35.00	100.00
	Tim	36	55.4167	38.47773	6.41296	42.3977	68.4357	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	62.5000	36.56487	5.17105	52.1084	72.8916	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	14	83.2143	18.35621	4.90590	72.6157	93.8128	35.00	100.00
	Tim	36	71.9444	13.69451	2.28242	67.3109	76.5780	35.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.1000	15.79492	2.23374	70.6111	79.5889	35.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	14	84.2857	18.89822	5.05076	73.3742	95.1972	50.00	100.00
	Tim	36	58.6111	37.71341	6.28557	45.8507	71.3715	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	65.8000	35.30277	4.99257	55.7671	75.8329	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	14	82.5714	16.57793	4.43064	72.9996	92.1432	55.67	100.00
	Tim	36	65.6944	21.53408	3.58901	58.4084	72.9805	39.00	94.67
	Total	50	70.4200	21.51125	3.04215	64.3066	76.5334	39.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Risk facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	11.698	1	15.567	.004
Recall	Welch	11.109	1	22.418	.003
FMeasure	Welch	.000	1	17.024	.984
Duration	Welch	3.118	1	16.319	.096
FirstActDet	Welch	4.677	1	15.888	.046
LastActDet	Welch	2.994	1	16.559	.102
ProcDur	Welch	.088	1	24.745	.769
FixRel	Welch	.301	1	23.117	.588
FixIrrel	Welch	.577	1	19.105	.457
AvDurRelFix	Welch	1.598	1	17.938	.222
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	.415	1	29.412	.524
TotSac	Welch	1.110	1	27.051	.302
Sac2Key	Welch	2.579	1	21.369	.123
AvAttention	Welch	.841	1	27.685	.367
AvMentWL	Welch	.014	1	18.523	.906
AvFam	Welch	1.973	1	23.199	.173
AvSCL	Welch	1.179	1	29.974	.286
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.034	1	18.159	.855
HRVar_NN50	Welch	2.526	1	27.259	.124
NASA_MD	Welch	4.481	1	20.118	.047
NASA_PD	Welch	.845	1	16.540	.371
NASA_TD	Welch	1.530	1	19.361	.231
NASA_Performance	Welch	7.908	1	38.486	.008
NASA_Effort	Welch	4.338	1	18.908	.051
NASA_Frustration	Welch	10.138	1	44.660	.003
NASA_Score	Welch	8.761	1	30.741	.006

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Learning style facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	12	.5200	.26399	.07621	.3523	.6877	.00	.90
	Tim	38	.4858	.19954	.03237	.4202	.5514	.11	.90
	Total	50	.4940	.21430	.03031	.4331	.5549	.00	.90
Recall	Abby	12	.5383	.27102	.07824	.3661	.7105	.00	.90
	Tim	38	.6342	.23253	.03772	.5578	.7106	.15	1.00
	Total	50	.6112	.24295	.03436	.5422	.6802	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	12	.4825	.20321	.05866	.3534	.6116	.00	.83
	Tim	38	.4864	.12567	.02039	.4451	.5277	.20	.70
	Total	50	.4855	.14560	.02059	.4441	.5268	.00	.83
Duration	Abby	12	2471.3333	716.49187	206.83339	2016.0961	2926.5706	1208.00	3150.00
	Tim	38	1575.7105	458.79972	74.42714	1424.9068	1726.5142	1060.00	2675.00
	Total	50	1790.6600	650.75907	92.03123	1605.7163	1975.6037	1060.00	3150.00
FirstActDet	Abby	12	487.2500	172.71686	49.85906	377.5109	596.9891	95.00	742.00
	Tim	38	152.0263	96.34944	15.62994	120.3570	183.6956	45.00	532.00
	Total	50	232.4800	186.07002	26.31427	179.5995	285.3605	45.00	742.00
LastActDet	Abby	12	2001.0000	878.57209	253.62191	1442.7819	2559.2181	675.00	3099.00
	Tim	38	1250.6842	555.10545	90.04999	1068.2256	1433.1428	654.00	2645.00
	Total	50	1430.7600	714.66212	101.06849	1227.6553	1633.8647	654.00	3099.00
ProcDur	Abby	12	470.3333	354.06505	102.20978	245.3711	695.2955	6.00	1105.00
	Tim	38	325.0263	301.27356	48.87302	226.0002	424.0525	6.00	1541.00
	Total	50	359.9000	317.19036	44.85749	269.7555	450.0445	6.00	1541.00
FixRel	Abby	12	1.8217	.67887	.19597	1.3903	2.2530	.90	2.85
	Tim	38	1.8731	.59889	.09715	1.6763	2.0700	.75	2.85
	Total	50	1.8608	.61220	.08658	1.6868	2.0348	.75	2.85
FixIrrel	Abby	12	3.0200	2.84022	.81990	1.2154	4.8246	.66	9.06
	Tim	38	5.5768	4.57443	.74207	4.0733	7.0804	.57	15.70
	Total	50	4.9632	4.33918	.61365	3.7300	6.1964	.57	15.70
AvDurRelFix	Abby	12	730.5700	382.23588	110.34199	487.7089	973.4311	225.29	1445.73
	Tim	38	551.9250	238.35137	38.66570	473.5809	630.2691	197.00	1177.00
	Total	50	594.7998	285.72228	40.40723	513.5984	676.0012	197.00	1445.73
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	12	934.7425	488.84150	141.11638	624.1474	1245.3376	179.65	1807.04
	Tim	38	743.2471	347.29129	56.33809	629.0953	857.3989	123.87	1982.39
	Total	50	789.2060	389.28707	55.05351	678.5718	899.8402	123.87	1982.39
TotSac	Abby	12	74.5833	11.84336	3.41888	67.0584	82.1082	57.00	93.00
	Tim	38	76.2368	11.54178	1.87232	72.4432	80.0305	54.00	95.00
	Total	50	75.8400	11.51460	1.62841	72.5676	79.1124	54.00	95.00
Sac2Key	Abby	12	34.0000	11.30567	3.26367	26.8167	41.1833	20.00	55.00
	Tim	38	35.7105	10.93200	1.77340	32.1173	39.3038	19.00	61.00
	Total	50	35.3000	10.93067	1.54583	32.1935	38.4065	19.00	61.00
AvAttention	Abby	12	.7750	.17123	.04943	.6662	.8838	.40	1.00
	Tim	38	.7342	.19628	.03184	.6697	.7987	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.7440	.18969	.02683	.6901	.7979	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	12	.6500	.22764	.06571	.5054	.7946	.30	1.00
	Tim	38	.7053	.18880	.03063	.6432	.7673	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6920	.19778	.02797	.6358	.7482	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	12	.3417	.17816	.05143	.2285	.4549	.10	.60
	Tim	38	.4132	.12980	.02106	.3705	.4558	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3960	.14422	.02040	.3550	.4370	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	12	784.1667	118.76014	34.28310	708.7101	859.6233	566.00	942.00
	Tim	38	792.7895	143.48748	23.27674	745.6263	839.9526	503.00	998.00
	Total	50	790.7200	136.84507	19.35282	751.8291	829.6109	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	12	43.0768	29.51202	8.51939	24.3257	61.8278	10.92	78.83
	Tim	38	42.7713	17.63815	2.86129	36.9738	48.5688	14.62	82.27
	Total	50	42.9240	23.57508	3.64034	35.6595	55.1983	12.77	80.55

	Total	50	42.8446	20.74739	2.93412	36.9483	48.7410	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	12	26.6662	21.19853	6.11949	13.1973	40.1351	2.81	56.57
	Tim	38	26.4813	20.06113	3.25435	19.8873	33.0752	.10	60.08
	Total	50	26.5257	20.11907	2.84527	20.8079	32.2434	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	12	88.3333	14.66804	4.23430	79.0137	97.6530	50.00	100.00
	Tim	38	79.4737	11.01531	1.78692	75.8530	83.0943	50.00	90.00
	Total	50	81.6000	12.43103	1.75801	78.0671	85.1329	50.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	12	31.2500	28.69313	8.28299	13.0193	49.4807	10.00	70.00
	Tim	38	20.3947	15.99753	2.59514	15.1365	25.6530	5.00	65.00
	Total	50	23.0000	20.00000	2.82843	17.3161	28.6839	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	12	79.1667	25.03028	7.22562	63.2632	95.0702	30.00	100.00
	Tim	38	40.6579	27.29150	4.42727	31.6874	49.6284	5.00	90.00
	Total	50	49.9000	31.29012	4.42509	41.0074	58.7926	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	12	89.5833	19.00458	5.48615	77.5084	101.6583	40.00	100.00
	Tim	38	53.9474	36.74525	5.96087	41.8695	66.0252	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	62.5000	36.56487	5.17105	52.1084	72.8916	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	12	84.5833	18.02250	5.20265	73.1324	96.0343	35.00	100.00
	Tim	38	72.1053	13.98027	2.26790	67.5101	76.7005	35.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.1000	15.79492	2.23374	70.6111	79.5889	35.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	12	90.4167	16.71395	4.82490	79.7971	101.0362	50.00	100.00
	Tim	38	58.0263	36.17785	5.86882	46.1350	69.9177	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	65.8000	35.30277	4.99257	55.7671	75.8329	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	12	87.7500	15.76156	4.54997	77.7356	97.7644	55.67	100.00
	Tim	38	64.9474	20.26795	3.28790	58.2855	71.6093	39.00	94.67
	Total	50	70.4200	21.51125	3.04215	64.3066	76.5334	39.00	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Learning style facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.171	1	15.180	.685
Recall	Welch	1.219	1	16.444	.286
FMeasure	Welch	.004	1	13.758	.950
Duration	Welch	16.601	1	13.964	.001
FirstActDet	Welch	41.160	1	13.230	.000
LastActDet	Welch	7.772	1	13.883	.015
ProcDur	Welch	1.645	1	16.351	.218
FixRel	Welch	.055	1	16.770	.817
FixIrrel	Welch	5.346	1	30.348	.028
AvDurRelFix	Welch	2.335	1	13.805	.149
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.588	1	14.675	.227
TotSac	Welch	.180	1	18.103	.676
Sac2Key	Welch	.212	1	17.988	.651
AvAttention	Welch	.481	1	20.951	.495
AvMentWL	Welch	.581	1	16.073	.457
AvFam	Welch	1.655	1	14.873	.218
AvSCL	Welch	.043	1	22.084	.837
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.001	1	13.570	.973
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.001	1	17.681	.979
NASA_MD	Welch	3.716	1	15.124	.073
NASA_PD	Welch	1.564	1	13.228	.233
NASA_TD	Welch	20.651	1	19.973	.000
NASA_Performance	Welch	19.350	1	36.980	.000
NASA_Effort	Welch	4.834	1	15.412	.044
NASA_Frustration	Welch	18.175	1	40.968	.000
NASA_Score	Welch	16.500	1	23.576	.000

a. Asymptotically F distributed.